

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

YASHIL ENERGIYA SEKTORIDA VENCHUR INVESTITSIYALARINING RIVOJLANISHI: GLOBAL TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTON IMKONIYATLARI	12
Qarajanova Gulnoza Tolliyevna	
MILLIY KOMPANIYALARNI BAYNALMILALLASHUV BOSQICHLARI VA XALQARO KORPORATIV BIRLASHUVLAR (M&A) STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	19
Shokirov Shoxruxmirzo Baxtiyorjon o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI IQLIM VA EKOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARGA MOSLASHTIRISHDA SMART TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	23
Mirzataev Salamat Muratbaevich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA MEVACHILIK KLASTERLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA RENTABELLIK KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	28
Tureev Azizbek Abatovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA QURILISH XIZMATLARINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK MODELI.....	32
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
TOG'-KON SANOATI KORXONALARIDA RESURS TEJAMKOR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	37
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL INSURANCE MARKET AND THE LEVEL OF INCLUSIVENESS.....	43
Ravshanova Mohinur O'rolovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI AJ KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	51
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdukarim qizi	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARI.....	55
Qaraev Anvar Botirovich	
THE IMPACT OF LOYALTY PROGRAMS ON CUSTOMER RETENTION IN ONLINE COSMETICS: A MIXED-METHODS STUDY	61
Toirova Mubina	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA "YASHIL" TRANSFORMATSIYANING JAHON MOLIYA BOZORLARIGA TA'SIRI.....	66
Qo'chqorova Muxlisaxon Ulug'bek qizi	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR - ELEKTRON TIJORAT SAYTLARI, MARKETPLEYSLAR VA MOBIL ILOVALARNING O'RNI.....	73
Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES JARAYONLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDAGI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	79
Abdulla Mavlonov	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI LOGISTIKASINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH ORQALI BOZOR INFRATUZILMASI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	82
Komekova Gulzira Sharbaevna	

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К АГРЕГИРОВАНИЮ РАЗРОЗНЕННЫХ ДАННЫХ В ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ	87
Бекматов Акмал Курбонмахматович	
SUG'URTA TASHKIOTLARIDA MHXSGA O'TISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	93
Azamatova G. I.	
O'ZBEKISTON SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHGA YO'NALTIRILGAN INVESTITSİYALARNING XARAJAT-FOYDA TAHLILI	98
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	104
Isxakova Sarvar Ayubovna	
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДОВ МАШИННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В КРЕДИТНОМ СКОРИНГЕ РОЗНИЧНЫХ ЗАЁМЩИКОВ: ОПЫТ АКБ «КАПИТАЛБАНК» (РЕСПУБЛИКА УЗБЕКИСТАН)	109
Жанайдарова Камола Абаевна	
INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA IPO VA KORPORATIV OBLIGATSIYALAR SAMARADORLIGI	115
G'afurov Sherzod Abdvaxob o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARNING AHAMIYATI	120
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL VODOROD IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING BIZNES VA INVESTITSION MEKANIZMLARI	123
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanaqulovna	
XUFYONA IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI: SOLIQ ISLOHOTLARI VA RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	130
Utkirova Jasmina Jasur qizi	
XORIJIY DAVLATLAR AMALIYOTIDA XUSUSIY INVESTITSİYALAR VA AHOLI DAROMADLARI O'RTASIDAGI MUTANOSIBLIKNI TARTIBGA SOLISH YO'NALISHLARI	135
Salimova Zaxro Sobirjon qizi	
QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI VA BASHORATI	141
Xakimov D.R.	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРОГРЕССА НА ЗАНЯТОСТЬ: ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ И ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ	151
Эркинбаева Камила Жавлонбековна	
TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	156
Tangirkulov Bekzod Boxadirovich	
HUDUDLARDA TURISTLARGA UMUMIY OVQATLANISH XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATISHNING SAMARALI RIVOJLANISH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: RFEI INDEKSI, KLASSTER MODEL I VA "TASTE UZBEKISTAN" RAQAMLI EKOTIZIMI	162
Maxmadiyeva Charos Xayrullayevna	
SAVDODA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARINING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	171
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
КЛИМАТИЧЕСКОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕЙ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	174
Лана Цхай	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARNI MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTDA AKS ETTIRISHNI MASALALARI	181
G'oziyeva Moxira Rustam qizi	

TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA LIDERLIK SAMARADORLIGINING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	189
Yuldashova Yoqutoy	
KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI RAQAMLI KREDITLASHNING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI	193
Karimova Aziza Maxomadrizoyevna Abduraxmonov Faridun Firo'z o'g'li	
SANOAT TARMOQLARIDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA KONSEPSIYASINING IQTISODIY VA INSTITUTSIONAL MAZMUNI	199
Mamarasulova Iroda Zafarjon qizi	
ESG-ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ПО ПРОИЗВОДСТВУ ПОЛИМЕРНОЙ УПАКОВКИ: ТЕОРИЯ, ОТРАСЛЕВАЯ СПЕЦИФИКА И МИРОВЫЕ ПРАКТИКИ.....	204
Ташпулатов Дильмурад Рустамович	
ENHANCING GREEN ACCOUNTING IN UZBEKISTAN: COMPARATIVE LESSONS FROM DEVELOPED ECONOMIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	210
Xolmurodova Durdona Otamurod qizi	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ, СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ И ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	218
Саттарова Зухра Илхомовна	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJLANISHINING HUDUDIY INVESTITSIYA FAOLLIGIGA TA'SIRI	224
Toirjonov Sardorbek Dilshodjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNING BANDLIKNI TA'MINLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI	229
Mamadaliyev Doniyorbek Shuhratbek o'g'li	
TOSHKENTDA KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI: LOGIT VA PROBIT MODELLARI ASOSIDA EMPIRIK TAHLIL	235
Hasan Ibragimov Mannonov Shahzod Toshmurod Qulmanov	
MOSLASHUVCHAN MENEJMENT VA UNING SIFAT BOSHQARUVIDAGI O'RNI	242
Ibroximova Zuhra Baxtiyor qizi	
IJTIMOIIY SOHANI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MINTAQAVIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	247
Ro'zmetov Kamol Ibodullayevich Ibragimov Qayumbek Ikromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIY TAJRIBALARI.....	254
Muminov Bekzod Polvonovich	
KORPORATIV AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH KONSEPSIYASINING NAZARIY EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR TASNIFI.....	263
Kuchkarov Ulug'bek Tahirovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MINTAQALARIDA EKSPORT FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	268
Abdulatifova Moxinur Alisher qizi	
FIZIKA FANINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA SAMARALI O'QITISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI.....	275
Razzoqov I.D.	
RAQAMLI MEHNAT BOZORLARI VA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIK: O'ZBEKISTON VA QOZOG'ISTON MISOLIDA QIYOSIY TAHLIL	281
Safarova Gulruh Akmal qizi	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ КАТЕГОРИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И НАУЧНЫЙ	

ПОДХОД К ЕЁ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ.....	287
Зайналов Ж. Р.	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI.....	293
Xolmatova Mumtozbeqim Alisherxon qizi	
TURISTIK BOZOR KONYUNKTURASINI O'RGANISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	298
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
PREPARATION OF NUT JAM USING MULBERRY SYRUP BASED ON ITS CONSUMER PROPERTIES.....	302
Pardaev Gayrat Yakhshibaevich	
BUXORO TARIXIY MARKAZIDAGI MEROS OBYEKTLARINING TURISTIK SIG'IM IMKONIYATLARI.....	306
Tolibova Shaxrizoda	
КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ НАУЧНО-АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЙ ОТЧЕТ: ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ, ФИНАНСОВАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СТРАХОВОГО РЫНКА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	314
Махмудов Комолиддин Розметович	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: THE SYNERGY OF INVESTMENT, AGRICULTURAL TRANSFORMATION, AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY.....	319
Kholmukhamedova Feruza	
IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA EKSPORT OPERATSIYALARINI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	324
Mir Axmadova Mariyam Nosir Axmadovna	
ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ЛИКВИДНОСТИ ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В РУСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	330
Бауетдинов Мажит Жанызакович	
Жанызакова Шахноза Мажит кызы	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	338
Kobilov Alisher	
Majidova Irodahon	
RAQAMLI UNIVERSITET MODELI — BARQAROR OLIY TA'LIMNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	346
Nazirova Komola Raximjon qizi	
HUDUD EKSPORTINING XOM ASHYOGA BOG'LIQLIGI: MOLIYAVIY OQIBATLAR VA BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	352
Norturayev Mansurbek Obid o'g'li	
MOLIYA BOZORINING IQTISODIY O'SISHDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	359
Maxkamova Dilafruz Aliyevna	
Miryunusov Avaz Iqboljon o'g'li	
ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM.....	363
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	

ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article explores the economic foundations for enhancing the efficiency of innovative services in the higher education system. The study examines the economic essence of higher education services, the contribution of innovation-oriented approaches to improving educational quality, and their relationship with human capital development and labour market demands. Particular attention is given to digital platforms, e-learning technologies, academic management systems, quality assurance mechanisms, and university–industry cooperation as key drivers of innovative service efficiency. The findings demonstrate that the development of innovative services in higher education serves as a strategic economic factor that promotes the efficient use of resources, improves educational quality, and supports the preparation of highly competitive specialists. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of financial sustainability, advanced digital infrastructure, and the innovative competencies of academic staff in strengthening the effectiveness and long-term development of innovative educational services.

Keywords: higher education, innovative services, educational services, economic efficiency, human capital, digital economy, university management, labour market, education quality, digital transformation.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'lim tizimida innovatsion xizmatlar samaradorligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari ilmiy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Unda innovatsion ta'lim xizmatlarining mazmun-mohiyati, raqamli texnologiyalar, universitet boshqaruvi, sifat monitoringi hamda mehnat bozori bilan integratsiyaning iqtisodiy samaradorlikka ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalari innovatsion xizmatlarning oliy ta'lim muassasalarida resurslardan samarali va oqilona foydalanish, ta'lim sifatini yuksaltirish, kadrlar tayyorlash jarayonini takomillashtirish hamda universitetlarning raqobatbardoshligini mustahkamlashdagi muhim ahamiyatini asoslab beradi. Shuningdek, innovatsion xizmatlarni rivojlantirishda moliyaviy barqarorlik, zamonaviy raqamli infratuzilma va professor-o'qituvchilarning innovatsion kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish ustuvor omillar sifatida e'tirof etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim, innovatsion xizmatlar, ta'lim xizmatlari, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, inson kapitali, raqamli iqtisodiyot, universitet boshqaruvi, mehnat bozori, ta'lim sifati, raqamli transformatsiya.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются экономические основы повышения эффективности инновационных услуг в системе высшего образования. Рассматриваются сущность инновационных образовательных услуг, влияние цифровых технологий, современных механизмов университетского управления, систем мониторинга качества и интеграции с рынком труда на экономическую эффективность образовательной деятельности. Результаты исследования подтверждают, что инновационные услуги являются важным фактором эффективного использования ресурсов, повышения качества образования, совершенствования подготовки кадров и укрепления конкурентоспособности высших учебных заведений. Особое внимание уделяется значению финансовой устойчивости, развитой цифровой инфраструктуры и инновационных компетенций профессорско-преподавательского состава как ключевых условий дальнейшего развития инновационных образовательных услуг.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, инновационные услуги, образовательные услуги, экономическая эффективность, человеческий капитал, цифровая экономика, управление университетом, рынок труда, качество образования, цифровая трансформация.

INTRODUCTION

At the current stage of socio-economic development, the higher education system serves not only as a social sphere but also as a strategic institution for human capital formation and the sustainable development of an innovation-driven economy. In the context of rapid digital transformation, universities are expected not only to provide high-quality theoretical knowledge but also to foster practical skills, innovative thinking, entrepreneurial culture, and advanced digital competencies among students. Consequently, the modernization of both the content and delivery mechanisms of higher education services has become a key priority.

Innovative services in higher education encompass e-learning platforms, distance education technologies, virtual laboratories, digital libraries, personalized learning pathways, start-up initiatives, research and innovation incubators, and collaborative programs linking universities with industry and business sectors. The effective implementation of these services contributes to enhancing educational quality, improving institutional performance, ensuring the efficient use of resources, and strengthening graduates' competitiveness in the labour market.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, comprehensive reforms are being carried out to modernize the education system, expand the use of digital technologies, and accelerate innovative development. The "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy identifies the development of digital infrastructure, the training of highly qualified personnel with digital skills, and the widespread adoption of advanced information technologies as strategic priorities for national development [1]. Furthermore, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 places special emphasis on improving the quality of education, developing the intellectual potential of young people, and promoting the practical implementation of innovative approaches in all sectors of society [2].

Against this background, the study of the economic foundations for enhancing the efficiency of innovative services in higher education is of considerable scientific and practical importance. The main purpose of this article is to identify the economic factors influencing the effectiveness of innovative services in higher education, assess existing opportunities and challenges, and develop scientifically grounded recommendations for their further improvement. The object of the research is the process of developing innovative services within the higher education system, while the subject of the study consists of the organizational, financial, and digital factors that determine their economic efficiency and long-term sustainability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of improving the efficiency of innovative services in higher education is closely associated with the development of the digital economy, human capital formation, the educational services market, and modern university management. A. Abdullayev highlights the economic importance of contemporary educational technologies within the digital economy and emphasizes that the digitalization of educational services contributes to cost optimization, increased accessibility, and the expansion of learning opportunities [3]. This perspective enables innovative services in higher education to be viewed not merely as technological tools but as strategic management mechanisms that enhance institutional efficiency and competitiveness.

D. Bell, in his theory of the post-industrial society, argues that knowledge, information, and scientific potential constitute the primary drivers of economic development [4]. Similarly, M. Castells demonstrates that network-based economies, communication technologies, and knowledge exchange play a crucial role in promoting sustainable economic growth in the information society [5]. These theoretical approaches provide a strong conceptual foundation for understanding the socio-economic significance of innovative service development in higher education.

A number of researchers have examined ways to improve the effectiveness of higher education systems, paying particular attention to the relationship between educational quality, management practices, and innovation-oriented mechanisms [6]. Their studies emphasize that service quality, student-centered approaches, digital monitoring systems, and flexibility in the educational process are among the key factors contributing to higher institutional performance and efficiency [7].

Other scholars have investigated the organization of the educational process through innovative approaches and have highlighted the positive impact of interactive pedagogical technologies and modern teaching methods on learning outcomes and student engagement [8]. Research on higher education development in the digital economy further indicates that the quality and effectiveness of university services are closely linked to labour market requirements, digital infrastructure development, and effective institutional governance [9].

In addition, Sh. Yo'ldashev explores innovation-driven development and digital transformation within the education system, emphasizing that digital technologies represent not only technical modernization but also a comprehensive transformation of teaching, assessment, management, and human resource development processes [10]. International studies likewise demonstrate that the efficiency of higher education services is

strongly connected with human capital development, the role of universities within innovation ecosystems, and the strengthening of cooperation between higher education institutions and the labour market [11].

Overall, the reviewed literature confirms that innovative services serve as a key factor in enhancing educational quality, increasing institutional efficiency, strengthening university competitiveness, and supporting sustainable socio-economic development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a systematic approach, comparative analysis, economic analysis, logical generalization, induction, and deduction methods. Through the systematic approach, innovative services in higher education are examined as an integrated system closely linked with university management, financial resources, digital infrastructure, the educational process, and labour market requirements.

The comparative analysis method is applied to evaluate the relative impact of traditional and innovative educational services on economic efficiency. In this context, key indicators such as operational costs, educational coverage, service quality, student engagement, digital monitoring capabilities, and graduates' adaptation to labour market demands are analyzed and compared.

Economic analysis is utilized to assess the contribution of innovative services to enhancing resource efficiency, reducing time and financial expenditures, automating academic processes, and strengthening the competitiveness of higher education institutions. Furthermore, the examination of regulatory documents and scientific literature provides a solid theoretical and practical basis for understanding the economic foundations of innovative educational services.

The combination of these research methods enables a comprehensive assessment of the factors influencing the effectiveness of innovative services and supports the development of evidence-based recommendations for their further improvement.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The effectiveness of innovative services in the higher education system is closely associated with the modernization of educational content and the continuous improvement of service delivery mechanisms. While traditional education primarily relies on classroom instruction, lectures, seminars, printed learning materials, and conventional assessment methods, innovative educational services increasingly integrate digital platforms, interactive content, distance learning technologies, personalized educational pathways, and practice-oriented projects.

The economic benefits of innovative services can be observed in several important dimensions.

The first dimension is cost optimization. Digital learning platforms and electronic resources significantly reduce the need for printed materials, excessive administrative procedures, and various organizational expenses. Although the establishment of digital infrastructure requires initial investment, these investments generate substantial long-term benefits by increasing flexibility, accessibility, and overall cost-effectiveness within the educational process.

The second dimension is the expansion of educational accessibility and coverage. Distance learning technologies, online courses, and digital libraries help overcome geographical barriers and provide broader access to educational opportunities. This is particularly beneficial for working students, individuals residing in remote regions, and professionals seeking continuing education and retraining. As access to education expands, the socio-economic returns on investments in human capital also increase.

The third dimension is the enhancement of quality assurance and monitoring systems. Digital platforms enable universities to monitor student participation, assignment completion, academic achievement, and teaching effectiveness in real time. As a result, managerial decisions can be based on accurate and objective data, fostering a culture of evidence-based governance and continuous quality improvement.

The fourth dimension is stronger integration with the labour market. Innovative services that incorporate practical projects, start-up incubators, employer-supported courses, professional certification programs, and internship opportunities contribute significantly to improving graduate employability. This demonstrates that the effectiveness of higher education services should be evaluated not only through academic outcomes but also through their contribution to long-term economic and professional success.

Overall, the findings indicate that innovative services play a vital role in improving educational quality, optimizing institutional resources, enhancing management effectiveness, and strengthening the competitiveness of both higher education institutions and their graduates in a rapidly evolving digital economy (Table 1).

Table 1
Impact of Innovative Services in Higher Education on Economic Efficiency¹

Type of Innovative Service	Economic Content	Impact on Efficiency	Expected Result
E-learning platforms	Organization of the educational process within a digital environment	Reduction of printing and administrative costs	A more cost-effective, flexible, and accessible educational process
Distance education services	Providing access to education regardless of geographical location	Expansion of educational coverage and accessibility	Increased participation in higher education services
Digital monitoring systems	Monitoring students' academic performance, engagement, and learning progress	Improved accuracy of managerial and academic decision-making	Enhanced quality assurance and educational effectiveness
Virtual laboratories	Development of practical skills through digital simulation technologies	Optimization of laboratory-related expenses	Expanded opportunities for practice-oriented learning
Start-up and incubation services	Support for students' innovative and entrepreneurial initiatives	Growth of innovation activity within universities	Development of entrepreneurial competencies and innovation culture
Cooperation with employers	Alignment of curricula with labour market requirements	Increased graduate employability and professional readiness	Preparation of highly competitive and skilled specialists

The table demonstrates that innovative services simultaneously perform several important economic functions within the higher education system. They contribute to cost optimization, broaden educational accessibility, accelerate management processes, and enhance practical learning outcomes for students. Moreover, the effectiveness of these services depends not only on their technological implementation but also on their successful integration into the overall strategic development framework of the university.

The financial sustainability of higher education institutions is another key factor supporting the successful development of innovative services. Modern digital platforms, virtual laboratories, electronic libraries, and start-up centers require adequate investment and continuous support. Therefore, alongside public funding, universities should actively utilize grants, research projects, private-sector partnerships, international cooperation programs, and additional educational services as complementary funding sources. The diversification of financial resources creates favorable conditions for the sustainable expansion of innovative services.

An equally important factor is the innovative competence of academic staff. The availability of digital platforms, electronic libraries, and virtual laboratories creates significant opportunities; however, their effectiveness largely depends on how successfully they are integrated into teaching and learning activities. Consequently, the continuous development of digital, pedagogical, and methodological competencies among academic staff plays a crucial role in maximizing the benefits of innovative services and improving educational outcomes.

At the same time, the ongoing development of innovative services in higher education opens broad opportunities for improving educational quality and institutional efficiency. Further enhancement of digital infrastructure, continuous improvement of educational content, wider use of electronic resources, and systematic development of academic staff's digital competencies can serve as important factors in increasing the effectiveness of innovative educational services. Moreover, strengthening practical cooperation with employers will ensure closer alignment between higher education and labour market needs. These measures will contribute to the sustainable development of higher education institutions, more efficient use of available resources, and the preparation of competitive specialists with modern knowledge and practical skills.

Therefore, evaluating the effectiveness of innovative services should extend beyond measuring technical capacity alone. Assessment criteria should also encompass educational quality, student satisfaction, graduate employability, cost-effectiveness, scientific and innovative activity, and the efficiency of digital management systems. Such a comprehensive approach allows universities to better align innovative services with their strategic objectives and socio-economic outcomes.

¹ Source: Developed by the author based on scientific literature and practical experiences in the higher education system.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Enhancing the efficiency of innovative services in higher education represents one of the key priorities of contemporary socio-economic development. In the era of the digital economy, universities increasingly serve not only as providers of knowledge but also as centers for human capital development, innovation generation, and the preparation of highly qualified specialists capable of meeting evolving labour market demands.

The findings of this study indicate that innovative services contribute significantly to cost optimization, expanded educational accessibility, improved quality assurance, more effective management processes, and stronger practical training for students. These benefits can be further amplified when innovative services are systematically integrated with university governance, financing mechanisms, pedagogical innovation, and labour market needs.

Based on the research findings, several recommendations can be proposed. First, higher education institutions should develop dedicated strategic programs focused on the advancement of innovative services. Second, comprehensive quality assessment criteria for digital platforms and electronic educational resources should be established. Third, the digital and innovative competencies of academic staff should be continuously strengthened through professional development initiatives. Fourth, collaboration with employers should be expanded through practical projects, internships, dual education models, and joint academic programs. Fifth, greater use should be made of grants, public-private partnerships, and international development programs to support the financing of innovative initiatives.

Furthermore, indicators such as student satisfaction, graduate employment rates, the level of educational digitalization, research productivity, innovation activity, and university–industry cooperation should be incorporated into performance evaluation systems. The application of these indicators enables a more accurate assessment of the economic and social value generated by innovative services.

Overall, the development of innovative services in higher education represents an effective pathway toward the efficient utilization of resources, continuous improvement of educational quality, and strengthening of human capital. Consistent advancement in this area will enhance university competitiveness, expand opportunities for training modern specialists, foster innovation-driven economic growth, and create a sustainable environment for scientific and technological development.

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